

New European Bauhaus Call for proposals for Citizen Engagement Activities

Project Acronym: SOCIAL4FOOD

**Project title: SOCIAL farming FOR stimulating transgenerational knowledge
transfer and production of typical local FOOD**

Deliverable 2.2: RESULTS OF THE OPEN DAY EVENT

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1. Executive summary

The SOCIAL4FOOD project aims at applying the principles of the New European Bauhaus to improve the contact between young generations and green public spaces, guided by the wisdom of the elders. Through a series of social farming activities, the project aims to stimulate the involvement of teenagers from the Town of Arsoli (including also young immigrants) in collaboratively farming and cooking a very ancient and high-quality bean typical of this town, named “fagiolina arsolana”.

The main purpose of this deliverable is to provide a comprehensive description of the results of the Open Day event that was organized and took place the 29th of July 2022 in Arsoli (RM). This event constitutes the first phase of the co-creation methodology based on the design thinking approach. This event engaged four different target groups of participants including local teenagers, local children aged 8-12 years, elders and local farmers in an attempt to identify experiences and ideas on the growing and cooking of the fagiolina arsolana.

The Open Day event contributes in:

- building the transgenerational dialogue and establishing a process of productive contamination, inspiration, and shared ideas between older and younger generations.*
- integrating people in the design of public services, and for the public, to hand down and/or learn the local traditions.*

2. The applied methodology

During the Open day event, the first stage (emphasize and define) of the co-creation methodology based on the design thinking approach, as described in Deliverable 3.1, was applied. Local teenagers, children aged 8-12 years, elders and farmers were involved in the storytelling of experiences on the growing and cooking of the "fagiolina arsolana" and the elicitation of ideas.

Specifically, two different sessions were organized to meet the needs of the different target groups: the former for adults and adolescents and the latter for children.

2.1. SESSION for ADULTS and ADOLESCENTS

In the first session, dedicated to adults and adolescents, the world café method was applied that consisted in the following activities: collection of experiences, elicitation of ideas, sharing of ideas, and voting of ideas.

Collection of experiences

Participants were asked to answer the following triggering questions, according to their experiences:

- 1) What is your most significant experience in the GROWING of the "fagiolina arsolana" (or in the growing of agricultural products in general)? What difficulties have you encountered? What were the positive aspects?
- 2) What is your most significant experience in the COOKING of the "fagiolina arsolana" (or of the typical cuisine of Arsoli in general)? What difficulties have you encountered? What were the positive aspects?

Different groups of participants were formed, taking care to include at least one member of each target user for each group: adult, adolescent, man and women.

Each person had a maximum of 3 minutes available to tell their experience. After 20 minutes, each participant had 10 minutes to write a brief description of the experience (2-3 sentences) on a post-it and the positive and negative aspects on two further post-its. The post-its have been attached to a poster for the final discussion.

Elicitation of ideas

Participants were asked to answer the following triggering questions, according to their ideas:

- 1) How to pass on the experience and skills necessary for the traditional growing and cooking of the "fagiolina arsolana" from local elders to adolescents?
- 2) How to stimulate the involvement of local teenagers (including young immigrants) in the collaborative growing and cooking of the "fagiolina arsolana"?

3) How would you like to organise the social farm? Who should be involved? How should the tasks be performed?

The different groups of participants appointed a spokesperson for illustrating the emerged ideas and a secretary for reporting the ideas that emerged for each question on sheets.

The groups had a maximum of 10 minutes available for discussing and proposing ideas that answered the 3 triggering questions.

Sharing of ideas

The post-it written by the different groups were put on a poster and the spokesperson of each group explains the ideas that emerged for each question.

Voting of ideas

Each participant was provided with 6 stickers to apply to the 2 ideas that he/she considered most relevant for each question (according to the level of appreciation). At the end of the vote, the most significant ideas, emerged from the discussion, have been summarized.

2.2. SESSION for CHILDREN

In the second section, dedicated to children, the storytelling method was applied that consisted of the following activities: storytelling of experiences with emotion definition, collection of tips, and drawings.

Storytelling of experiences

Two rounds of storytelling have been organized: the former for the experiences in the cultivation of the “fagiolina arsolana” and the latter for its cooking.

In the first round, participants were divided into different groups; they were asked to tell their experience with the growing of garden products (in particular the “fagiolina arsolana”). Some possible examples were given (I sowed vegetables with my father/grandfather, I attended the bean harvest event, I sowed seedlings with my teachers, etc.). After the storytelling, participants were asked to write 1-2 sentences to describe their experience. Finally, each participant were provided with 5 stickers representing the smiles with the emotions (very happy, happy, indifferent, sad, and very sad) and were asked to apply them to the written experience (according to their level of satisfaction).

In the second round, the same process has been followed focusing on the experiences in the cooking of the “fagiolina arsolana”.

Collection of tips

Participants were asked to answer the following triggering questions, according to their ideas:

1) What would you like to do to learn how to grow the “fagiolina arsolana”?

2) What would you like to do to learn how to cook the “fagiolina arsolana”?

Some possible examples were given (e.g., cultivating a vegetable garden with my companions, making a laboratory to learn, listening to the stories experienced by the elderly, etc.)

Drawings

Each participant was asked to realize a drawing that represents his/her experience.

3. Obtained results

The Open day event was attended by 38 people belonging to the target groups described in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Target groups that attended the Open day event

Considering the gender dimension of the participants, the event was attended by 14 women (37%) and 24 men (63%), as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Gender of participants to the Open day event

In this section, the results of the two sessions organized during the Open Day event are described in detail.

3.1. Results of the session for adults and adolescents

The session for adults and adolescents was attended by 22 people belonging to the target groups described in Figure 1. In the following paragraphs, the results obtained in the different phases of the applied methodology, described in Section 2, are provided.

Collection of experiences

Considering the first triggering question related to the most significant experience in the growing of the “fagiolina arsolana” (or in the growing of agricultural products in general), most of the participants (37% of respondents) had direct experience in the growing of the fagiolina, while 5 participants (31.25% of respondents) did not have any growing experience, 2 participants (12.5%) had direct experience in the growing of other agricultural products, and other 2 participants (12.5%) had a non-direct experience but they observed people growing the fagiolina (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Participants' experience in the growing of the “fagiolina arsolana”

Considering the second triggering question related to the most significant experience in the cooking of the “fagiolina arsolana” (or in the typical recipes of Arsolì in general), 4 participants (36% of respondents) had direct experience in the cooking of the fagiolina, while the other ones only had experience in tasting recipes with the fagiolina (4 respondents – 36%) or observing people cooking the fagiolina (3 participants – 27%) (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Participants' experience in the cooking of the "fagiolina arsolana"

Considering the difficulties that participants have encountered during their experiences, a total of 15 responses have been provided, as shown in Figure 5.

Among the difficulties, the most cited ones were: the lack of knowledge (26.6%); problems related to the environment, fauna and climate (20%) followed by the shortage of the fagiolina (13.3%) and the lack of involvement of young people (13.3%). The following are some sentences reported by participants:

The lack of experience makes cultivation process more difficult

Negative aspects are linked to climate change and the difficulty in managing the fauna that cause considerable damage to crops

A negative aspect is the non-involvement of young people who seem almost exempt from the fagiolina traditions

Among the reported difficulties, even if with a lower response rate, there were also: the physical effort, the product properties (hard skin), the poor valorisation and the low economic return (each one received 1 response (6.7%)). Among the sentences reported by participants are the following:

The cultivation of the fagiolina requires a demanding physical effort

I find difficult to cook the fagiolina (due to its hardness)

The territory and the lack of development and cooperation do not allow to reach sustainable economic levels

Figure 5: Difficulties encountered during growing/cooking experiences

With respect to the positive aspects of the lived experience highlighted by participants, a total of 21 responses have been provided, as shown in Figure 6.

Among the positive aspects, the most cited by participants were the sense of belonging to the community and the territory (5 participants – 23.8%) and the importance to pass on the tradition of the fagiolina (4 participants – 19%). The fagiolina arsolana is a typical product so it is intrinsically linked to the territory and the community of Arsoli, which indicates not only a physical place but a lot of attributes (such as history, knowledge, experience and processing techniques) that have their roots in the tradition that is important to pass on to new generations. Below some sentences reported by participants:

The fagiolina is a typical local product and a source of pride for the community;

It is important to pass on the cultural baggage especially through young people;

The fagiolina is at risk of extinction, it is necessary to recover and enhance it thanks to the work of a whole community.

Other positive aspects highlighted by 9 participants (42.5%) are the contact with nature, the physical activity and some properties of the fagiolina (e.g., digestibility/taste). Some sentences reported by participants are shown below:

The positive aspect I found in cultivation was the pleasure of working outdoors

I rediscovered the harmony between man and nature

The positive aspect I found in cultivation was the pleasure of working outdoors

It is very easy to cook the fagiolina because of its thin skin

The fagiolina is a very tender bean so it is very digestible

Among the reported positive aspects, even if with a lower response rate (3 participants - 14.3%), there were also the stress reduction, the socialization and the economic revenue. Some sentences reported by participants are the following:

It is an excellent antidote to weekly work stress

The positive aspect of the experience, was being together with friends and producers and exchanging ideas and opinions

Another positive aspect was having had income from crops

Figure 6: Positive aspects highlighted by participants

Elicitation of ideas

After the collection of experiences, all participants were involved in the second phase of elicitation of ideas. Three further triggering questions were asked to the participants that have been divided in four groups (A, B, C and D).

Considering the ideas emerged in response to the first triggering question (i.e., how to pass on the experience and skills necessary for the traditional cultivation and cooking of the “fagiolina arsolana” from local elders to adolescents?), the implementation of agricultural practices in the lands was the most common idea in the various groups. In particular, the most voted ideas, provided by group A, were devoted to organise events for illustrating the different phases of the cultivation involving young people in a practical way (see Figure 7).

Groups B and D underlined the importance of setting up dedicated training events promoted by the municipal body and local schools, while groups A and C underlined the importance of involving the elderly for teaching the agricultural practices to young generations.

TRIGGERING QUESTION: How to pass on the experience and skills necessary for the traditional cultivation and cooking of the “fagiolina arsolana” from local elders to adolescents?		
Group A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To organise events to illustrate the different phases of the cultivation involving young people To organise events in which children are taught the cultivation of the fagiolina in a practical way 	9 votes
Group B	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To set up training days dedicated to the cultivation and harvesting of fagiolina and local products To restore abandoned vegetable gardens To organise initiatives promoted by the municipal body through the involvement of older and younger generations To draw on economic resources made available through projects financed by public administrations 	3 votes
Group C	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The implementation of agricultural practices in the land is the best teaching practice for handing down to young generation; the prospect of creating incomes from crops deriving as a stimulus to the new generations in order to continue the cultivation of the fagiolina while maintaining traditional and natural practices 	6 votes
Group D	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organize events to involve adolescents and adults involving local schools and neighboring countries that do not know the fagiolina 	6 votes

Figure 7: Ideas of participants related to the first triggering question

Considering the second triggering question (i.e how to stimulate the involvement of local teenagers (including young immigrants) in the collaborative cultivation and cooking of the “fagiolina arsolana”?), the organization of events open to the public involving young people was the most recurrent idea proposed by the various groups. In particular, the most voted ideas provided by group D were devoted to organize events where farmers illustrate the different phases of the fagiolina growing by promoting at the same time knowledge of the history of the fagiolina to the youngest for their practical implementation (see Figure 8). In particular, groups A and D suggested organizing events in the school, while group B was

more focused on spreading the fagiolina tradition on social media. Finally, group C focused on creating school camps for creating synergy between old generations and new farmers.

TRIGGERING QUESTION: How to stimulate the involvement of local teenagers (including young immigrants) in the collaborative cultivation and cooking of the “fagiolina arsolana”?		
Group A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organization of events in the schools 	6 votes
Group B	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open events • Diffusion of the tradition through social media and digital tools 	5 votes
Group C	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Realization of school camps for creating synergy between old generations and new farmers 	1 vote
Group D	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organization of events where farmers illustrate the different phases of the growing of the fagiolina to the youngest • Dissemination of the history of the fagiolina • Implementation of the different phases of the growing of the fagiolina by the young people • Tasting of the fagiolina 	11 votes

Figure 8: Ideas of participants related to the second triggering question

Considering the third triggering question (i.e. how would you like to organise the social farm? Who should be involved? How should the tasks be performed?), the most common idea in the various groups was to involve local associations that help in the growing of the fagiolina. In particular, the most voted ideas are provided by groups B and D and are devoted to involve local associations mainly composed of elderly people with strong experience (group B) but also young people including people with disabilities (group D). Moreover, groups A and B emphasized the importance of following the experience of farmers and the elderly to undertake a specific agricultural activity, but also stimulating the collaboration of all the participants in the initiative. Group C stressed the importance of buying tools to improve and expand cultivation in the following years, while group D highlighted the importance of involving all people who want to work in the countryside, mainly people with disabilities and young people who are not busy with school activities during the summer.

TRIGGERING QUESTION: How would you like to organise the social farm? Who should be involved? How should the tasks be performed?		
Group A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The responsibility and organization should be of the most experienced people but the collaboration could be of all and the proceeds can be used during the festival of the fagiolina 	3 votes
Group B	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To involve the local associations in the cultivation of the fagiolina to reactivate abandoned lands by involving the experience of the elderly for guiding the younger generations in the specific agricultural activities To organize several groups for establishing: who prepares the ground with fallow; who takes care of the planting; who takes care of the growth phase and maintenance of the planting; who is in charge of the collection phase It is important to ensure that all participants are involved in the various operational phases. The most appropriate means to give employment development is the establishment of a small social cooperative that uses its resources in the cultivation of all local products. 	9 votes
Group C	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To identify a land of the municipality to cultivate the fagiolina by creating groups made up of elderly and young people for management; To organize local associations that are held in the cultivation phase. To purchase tools to improve and expand the cultivation 	7 votes
Group D	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To involve people who want to get involved and work in the countryside, people with disabilities and young people who are not busy with school during the summer period can be involved. The main role must be given to the person with the most experience (local producer). 	9 votes

Figure 9: Ideas of participants related to the third triggering question

Sharing of ideas

The post-it written by the different groups were put on a poster and the spokesperson of each group explained the ideas that emerged for each question. Some photos of the discussion are provided in Appendix A.

Voting of ideas

Each participant applied 2 stickers to the 2 ideas considered most relevant for each question. The votes obtained by the different ideas are reported in Figures 7, 8, and 9.

Some photos of the sessions for adults and adolescents are provided in the Appendix A.

3.2. Results of the session for children

The session for children was attended by 16 children. In the following paragraphs, the results obtained in the different phases of the applied methodology, described in Section 2, are provided.

Storytelling of experiences

Considering the first question on the experience with the growing of garden products (in particular the “fagiolina arsolana”), a total of 16 responses have been collected. Most of the participants (69% of respondents) had direct experience in the growing of the fagiolina, while 3 participants (19% of respondents) had direct experience in the growing of other agricultural products (e.g., corn, tomatoes, eggplant, and zucchini), and only 1 participant did not have any growing experience (6 %) or had a non-direct experience (observation of people while growing the fagiolina) (6%) (see Figure 10).

Figure 10: Children' experiences in the growing of the fagiolina arsolana

With respect to the second question about the experiences in the cooking of the “fagiolina arsolana”, 7 participants (50% of respondents) had direct experience in the cooking of traditional foods (e.g. hand-made pasta and typical sweets), while the other ones had a direct experience in the cooking of the fagiolina (4 participants - 28%), a non-direct experience (observation of people (e.g. grand-mother) while cooking the fagiolina (2 participants –14%)) or did not have any cooking experience (1 participant – 7%) (see Figure 11).

Figure 11: Children' experience in the cooking of the fagiolina arsolana

The growing experiences have been evaluated by children in a positive way, as shown in Figure 12. The majority of children were happy (63%) or very happy (25%) to have lived the experience, while only 6% of children were very sad or indifferent. This data has been extracted from the smiles that each child applied to his/her written experience (according to their level of satisfaction).

Figure 12: Children' emotion felt during the lived experiences

Collection of tips

After the collection of experiences, all children were involved in the second phase of collection of tips. Two further questions were asked to children. Note that each participant could provide more than one answer to the questions.

Considering the first question (i.e. what would you like to do to learn how to grow the "fagiolina arsolana"?), a total of 21 responses have been provided, as shown in Figure 13.

The most common idea proposed by children was organizing laboratories/courses with friends/relatives (8 children - 38%), followed by cultivating a vegetable garden with relatives

(6 children – 29%), friends (3 children – 14%) or a farmer (3 children – 14%), and listening to passionate people with experience (1 child – 5%).

Figure 13: Children' tips for learning how to grow the fagiolina arsolana

Considering the second question (i.e., what would you like to do to learn how to cook the “fagiolina arsolana”?), a total of 16 responses have been provided, as shown in Figure 14.

The most common tip proposed by children was organizing laboratories/courses/lessons (7 children - 44%), followed by having a cooking experience with friends/relatives (4 participants - 25%) and elderly people (3 participants – 19%), and observing experienced/passionate people (2 participants – 12%).

Figure 14: Children' tips for learning how to cook the fagiolina arsolana

Drawings

The photos of the drawings that children realized for representing their cooking/growing experience are provided in Appendix B, along with some photos of the sessions for children.

Appendix A

In this section, some photos of the session for adults and adolescents are provided.

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Appendix B

In this section, the drawings that children realized for representing their cooking/growing experience, along with some photos of the sessions for children are provided.

